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"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

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Situating and estimating interdisciplinary exchange at the University of Antwerp

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Introduction

Interdisciplinarity has occupied a central place in science policy contexts for quite some time now. In Flanders, from 2024 onwards a parameter for it could also be added to the BOF-key, the main funding distribution mechanism used by the government for its decisions on financing of the five Flemish research Universities (Luwel, 2021). This would make interdisciplinarity a quasi-prerequisite for funding and put it on the same level as international collaboration in science and research excellence. The premise is that this indicator for interdisciplinarity (or IDR in brief) will stimulate the institutions to undertake such research. As many will contend however, IDR is not all that new. At the University of Antwerp, one of the five Flemish research universities, for example, IDR occupies a central place in both research and education.

This short research in progress note aims at describing which initiatives have been developed by the University of Antwerp to facilitate and further stimulate interdisciplinary knowledge exchange, and how the University aims to proceed in mapping and indicating these exchanges. We first briefly discuss initiatives taken in an educational context (e.g., the organization of bachelors and masters curricula). Next, we take a look at the research side: we discuss the organization of doctoral programs, innovative initiatives on the institutional level, and interdisciplinary research projects. For each aspect we propose different indicators or mapping strategies which can be used to identify IDR trends or patterns. As we will see, IDR is multifaceted and can be pursued on many fronts. We therefore stress the complexity of the concept and the importance of a reflexive and qualitative approach parallel to quantitative estimation.

Interdisciplinarity in education

There are currently 5 masters' degree programs and one postgraduate degree which have the explicit intent of being interdisciplinary. The organization of the curricula offered within these programs is either a shared initiative between different departments and/or faculties, or organized by an interdisciplinary institute (e.g., institute of environment and sustainable development). The University also insists on offering compulsory-elective courses to students on topics which are said to be interdisciplinary by default. Examples include: City and Diversity, Media and Digital Society, or Poverty and Inequality. Other interdisciplinary bottom-up initiatives are organized in an ad hoc fashion. The international design week initiated by the

faculty of design sciences attracts masters' students from different programs to think about pressing societal issues. IPSIG is a project organized by the faculty of medical and health sciences aiming at educating students about inter- and multidisciplinary collaboration in health care. Extra-curricular interdisciplinary summer schools are organized by the university covering topics of interest to almost all disciplines (e.g., the sustainable city, From Mine to Finger). Additionally, students from all master programs are offered the opportunity to write an interdisciplinary masters' thesis. The degree of interdisciplinarity of these initiatives could be approximated by looking at disciplinary distributions in student enrolment numbers and educational background as well as the affiliation and research portfolios of teaching staff. Of main interest here however is what the outcomes and impact of these educational initiatives are. We could for example query which skills both students and faculty obtain. A relevant insight would also result from analyzing if students enrolled in interdisciplinary courses or programs have higher chances of finding a job.

Interdisciplinarity in research

Doctoral degrees

To further encourage interdisciplinary research a separate classification for it has been established in the Flemish Universities' (including UAntwerp) doctoral education legislation (see https://medialibrary.uantwerpen.be/files/53711/deafbde2-3e34-435e-a2fe-833e07cfb8ac.pdf?_ga=2.232764383.1132027969.1650879616-1283461675.1642666449, chapter 6). Apart from this formal move there are also separate funding initiatives being installed at the universities (e.g., DOCPRO at UAntwerp). The promise there is that the involvement of two supervisors from different research institutes or faculties (with a large enough distance between their subjects of interest) could lead to breakthroughs in both fields. In other words, a new synergy could result from an IDR doctoral project. While it is relatively straightforward to establish if the supervisors involved are affiliated to different organizational units, the aspects of cognitive distance and synergy are more difficult to indicate bibliometrically.

The aspect of cognitive distance has for example been approached by applying topic modeling to thesis abstracts in order to investigate if a particular dissertation is positioned 'between' discipline categories and could therefore be considered interdisciplinary (Nanni, Dietz and Ponzetto, 2018) or by looking at reference data. Synergy can be approached quantitatively by studying bibliographic coupling patterns (Leydesdorff and Ivanova, 2021). In addition to information on organizational affiliation of supervisors, the latter two bibliometric approaches could thus offer useful and complementary information about the extent to which interdisciplinary PhDs are indeed on the rise.

Research projects

GOA projects (*Geconcentreerde Onderzoeksacties* in Dutch or Concentrated Research Actions) are large-scale research projects with a duration of four years. Teams are formed consisting of researchers originating from at least two research groups at the UAntwerp. On a yearly basis 11 or 12 GOA projects are being developed at the University, accounting for +- 3 million euros in funding. Mapping the outcomes of these projects in terms of scientific and societal impact would allow us to develop a better understanding of the full potential of interdisciplinary research. While funding bodies like the European Research Council and the Research Foundation Flanders acknowledge the importance of interdisciplinary projects, scientometric research has for example raised doubts about funding success for interdisciplinary proposals (Seeber, Vlegels, & Cattaneo, 2022). If interdisciplinary research would indeed lead to more scientific innovation and contributions to societal issues than departmentalized disciplinary

science, it would be of crucial importance to determine if such projects indeed have lower chances of obtaining funding from bodies external to the University. It would allow the University of Antwerp to further develop its current position as a stronghold of interdisciplinary and innovative research.

Institutional initiatives

The University of Antwerp hosts 15 consortia of research excellence. These consortia offer space to researchers originating from different disciplines in order to enable interdisciplinary exchange. In addition, three research institutes are explicitly interdisciplinary: IMDO – Institute for environment and sustainable development, USI – Urban Studies Institute, and ARIA – Antwerp Research Institute in the Arts. There are also multidisciplinary valorization domains (AUHA) which are organized as such that professors from different research groups and departments with a track record in valorization are involved. What would be of relevance for these institutional initiatives is developing methods that might aid academics in finding the right research collaborators. Science mapping techniques making use of portfolio analysis, citation network analysis, or topic modeling could offer birds-eye views of the research landscape at the University of Antwerp and help interdisciplinary research units to find the right partners to answer their questions.

Conclusion

At the university of Antwerp, there already exists a great diversity in IDR initiatives and institutes, both on the teaching and research side. As described in this short note, a first task consists of mapping the outcomes of these initiatives on the one hand, and situating and indicating the sites of potential exchange on the other. We do however recognize the risk of standardizing what interdisciplinarity must mean (Rafols, 2019). Therefore, after this exploratory stage of mapping and indicating interdisciplinarity on different fronts, we propose to foster a co-creation model of evaluation in which we situate and co-define interdisciplinary practice together with teachers, researchers, students, and also stakeholders external to the university eco-system in order to further encourage it (Marres & de Rijcke, 2020). The future role of research administrators and policymakers in the context of stimulating IDR at the University of Antwerp would then be one of grasping the different meanings of IDR in different contexts and building bridges between relevant actors engaged in interdisciplinary practice.

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